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Project Deliverable

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides documentation regarding scientific reporting on consumer data's potential as a tool for lifestyle assessment.

The deliverable is mainly reported through a comprehensive paper describing:

1. The methodology needed to facilitate evidence-based, consumer-friendly lifestyle advice, including data handling and validation processes, secure optimal product data handling, processing, cleaning and validation, and exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives as accessed by consumer data.

The paper has been accepted by Nature Scientific Reports entitled: **"Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, The My Purchases cohort"**.

This report further details the status of other unpublished works connecting the abovementioned exposures to health-related outcomes or the absence of such outcomes.

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1. Introduction

WP4 is a high-risk, high-gain project in HEAP. WP4 aims to explore the feasibility of using consumer purchase data to continuously model and assess the impact of household consumed exposure on health and to use results to develop lifestyle communication models supporting lasting habit change.

Consumer purchase data are available through loyalty and credit card-based solutions in several EU countries. The legislation in Denmark enables the collection and use of personal non-anonymized consumer data, provided informed consent.

SSI has developed an electronic E-consent solution that allows citizens to transfer consumer data from private receipt providers to research.

WP4 recruits participants from a Danish commercial e-receipt provider, which is used by more than 1.1 million Danes. The e-receipts platform allows consumer data collection from 3 of Denmark's four largest retail chains.

Deliverable 4.1 described the recruitment of participants, using the framework to collect consumer data. D4.2 describes consumer data's potential as a tool for lifestyle assessment, including the methodology needed to facilitate evidence-based, consumer-friendly lifestyle advice and report on potential exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives as accessed by consumer data and association to health-related outcomes or absence of such outcomes.

In addition, this deliverable describes the recruitment status, the attempts to increase recruitment, and the choice to mitigate the effects of slow recruitment by collaborating with another Danish cohort.

The deliverable is mainly reported through a comprehensive paper describing the methodology needed to collect, enrich and analyse consumer data. The paper has been accepted by Nature Scientific Reports entitled: "Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, The My Purchases cohort".

The deliverable details the status of further scientific work in 2024, where the focus will be on disseminating two papers focusing on exposure to chemicals and additives as accessed by consumer data and nutrients and

association to health-related outcomes or the absence of such outcomes.

2. Work progress and unexpected risks.

As described in a previous deliverable, the COVID-19 pandemic coincided with the start of the HEAP project and caused considerable delays in the recruitment process. SSI is a preparedness institute, and most SSI resources were redirected towards handling the pandemic. Apart from low access to personnel, COVID-19-related work tasks caused bottlenecks.

HEAP Resource utilisation was adjusted to the situation, and from the beginning of 2021, there has been good progress, as previously described.

Another unexpected task was that the recruitment system had to be redesigned due to incompatibility between the previous version and the new digital signature solution in Denmark (NemID was changed to MitID). The new version was successfully deployed in 2023. As a result of the challenges above, recruitment has been lower than expected. 500+ participants have been recruited from existing initiatives described in D4.1. The planned mitigation in 2023 was to request approval to include consumer data from the Danish National Birth Cohort. Due to reservations regarding the use of a private partner (Storebox) to collect consumer data from a subset of participants, the Danish National Birth Cohort board did not approve this approach. Instead, a collaboration with the other Danish consumer data cohort, SMIL, which also collects data from Storebox, has been initiated. Access to this dataset has been granted, and analysis is now underway using the consumer data pipeline and analytic framework developed on the My Purchases cohort.

3. Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, The My Purchases cohort

The paper describes the methodology for facilitating evidence-based, consumer-friendly lifestyle advice, including data handling and validation processes.

Secure optimal product data handling, processing, cleaning and validation, and exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives as accessed by consumer data are described in depth in the paper, "Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, The My Purchases cohort" [1].

The paper integrates the deliverables and main tasks carried out by WP4. It describes:

1. The solution to collect consumer data as previously described in D4.1
2. The pipeline enabling data handling, processing, cleaning and validation of the consumer data streams
3. The "My Purchases" cohort participants' exposure to nutrients, chemicals, and additives, as accessed by consumer data
4. The potential of consumer data as a tool for lifestyle assessment, including the methodology needed to facilitate evidence-based, consumer-friendly lifestyle advice

The paper is published as open source, with related GitHub documentation, code and data:

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-023-47534-6#Sec28>

Figure 3.1 from the publication illustrates the concept.

Figure 3.1

- 1) Recruitment of participants who consent to the continuous transfer of individual/household level CPD
- 2) Establishment of near real-time pipelines, identification of the products sold, and enrichment of each product to enable broad assessment and identification of product type, ingredients, nutrients, intended and/or unintended chemicals, etc.
- 3) Retrieval of individual-level information about health outcomes and trajectories
- 4) Analysis of the impact of household consumer exposures on health

4. Exposure to chemicals and additives as accessed by consumer data

Significant efforts have been made to map, measure, and, in some cases, limit the population's exposure to several chemicals over time to investigate related health outcomes [2].

These include perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances, commonly referred to as PFAS, are synthetic chemicals that can be found in a wide variety of consumer products, the majority of which are non-degradable, thus making it a challenge to study the health effects of exposure to these "forever" chemicals [3]. Additionally, the European Union (EU) has approved over 300 chemicals for use in food, most of which are found in highly processed, non-organic products [4] and can be found in a large range of food products available to consumers [5]. To understand how widespread these chemicals are in the environment and consumer products, and how they affect human health, it is paramount to be able to measure exposures. Several initiatives to map harmful chemicals have been carried out by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) [6], the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) [7], as well as the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [8] and in the Nordic Countries [9].

Measuring the exposure to potentially harmful chemicals among consumers is a persistent challenge faced in efforts to secure a non-toxic environment. This comes from a lack of information regarding consumers' usage patterns regarding personal- and household-care products. One strategy developed and validated within the last decade is using consumer purchase data (CPD) as a proxy for product usage and/or consumption patterns and, thereby, a measure of exposure [10, 11]. In this study, we plan to use the My Purchases cohort, as previously described [1], to investigate exposure to certain consumer chemistry based on electronic receipts from purchases from select vendors in Denmark.

Objectives/Aims

The paper describes the variation among individual/household exposure profiles over time and the associations between exposures and self-reported health. Using self-reported disease, we aim to detect if any individuals have chemistry footprints that could ameliorate or aggravate their disease status using near real-time recommendations based on CPD.

Select preliminary results

436 individuals were recruited via the My Purchases website (mineindkob.ssi.dk) and consented to participation. 15 % of products sold were suspected of containing endocrine disruptors (ED), according to REACH, and 26 % of products were labelled C-class, according to Kemiluppen. These numbers come with high variation in individual profiles, as illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1

Figure 4.1 illustrates the large variation in total observed exposures among participants.

While some exposure groups were more pronounced among certain individuals (e.g., nicotine products, tobacco, other), the chemical exposures ranged across multiple exposure categories over time, highlighting participants' varied and unique chemical exposure footprint.

Taking a closer look at one exposure group, i.e. cigarette smoking, we can assess cumulative exposures over time per individual.

Figure 4.2

Figure 4.2 displays smoking purchase profiles over time, highlighting the possibility of monitoring chemical exposures over time using consumer purchases.

Plan for 2024: Initial results are promising, and we are awaiting an update to access GS1 data, which will allow us to add food ingredient information to the analysis. After this, we will update the results and publish and disseminate them.

5. Exposure to nutrients and association to health-related outcomes or absence of such outcomes.

The paper describes the variation among individual/household exposure profiles over time and the associations between exposures and self-reported health. Using self-reported disease, we aim to detect if any individuals have chemistry footprints that could ameliorate or aggravate their disease status using near real-time recommendations based on CPD.

Since 1990, there has been a marked shift towards a greater non-communicable diseases burden and a demographic shift towards an elderly population [12]. Commercial sector products such as Tobacco, alcohol, and ultra-processed food have been linked to poor health [13]. Some studies have concluded that consumers are incentivised to buy unhealthy rather than healthy food products [14], and an analysis of major supermarkets' corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategies verifies that health is not a major CSR goal [15]. Contrary to this, interventions in a supermarket setting could change consumer behaviour, provided that sustainable strategies are employed [16]. As more consumers use loyalty programs and digital receipts, consumer purchase data could help measure commercial determinants of health by analysing household lifestyle exposures and health outcomes [1] and may even be used to influence shopping behaviour in a healthy direction [17].

Studies have shown a good correlation between consumer data and food frequency questionnaires (FFQ) when a high coverage of purchases is reached [18-20]. On a population level, consumer purchases have been linked to major chronic diseases and conditions [21], but there seems to be a lack of comprehensive research examining the direct links between consumer purchase data and chronic health outcomes. Despite successful use as a tool to solve food-borne outbreaks and promising simulation studies in this field [22, 23], previous studies using individual data have not been totally aligned with previous FFQ-based results in the same field, either as a result of underreporting certain product groups in FFQs or bias relating to collecting CPD [24].

Here, we will analyse consumer purchase data and health outcomes from Danish registers, such as admission to hospitals or the initiation of novel treatment targeting chronic diseases [1].

This study aims to identify consumer purchase patterns associated with disease-free survival. We hypothesise that major known determinants of health, such as tobacco smoking and high alcohol consumption, are associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases.

Select preliminary results

The study will utilise the SMIL cohort. The cohort features 11,893 participants linked to their household members. Table 5.1 gives examples of outcomes, i.e., cardiovascular disease (CVD).

Table 5.1 Cohort outcomes among participants and households

Outcomes	Donates CPD	Persons in households of participants	Total
	N=11893	N=22342	N=30622
No CVD prior to 2019 *	8280	15646	23926
No CVD 2019-2021	8058 (67.8%)	15495 (69,4%)	23,553 (76.9%)
CVD 2019-2021	222 (1.9%)	151 (0.7%)	373 (1.2%)
1+ CVD prior to 2019	3613	3083	6696
No new CVD 2019-2021	3147 (26.5%)	2803 (12,5%)	5950 (19.4%)
New CVD 2019-2021	466 (3.9%)	280 (1,3%)	746 (2.4%)
% are columns totals			

Planned analytical approach

We will use an analytical approach developed from the My Purchases cohort.

The following figures are based on data from the 515 participants in My Purchases cohort and demonstrate the main analytical approach that will be run with the SMIL cohort.

Figure 5.1

Figure 5.1 Decision tree of the average monthly purchases among broadly defined food categories using the My Purchases cohort. The left leaves indicate that the statement above is true, and the right leaves indicate that the statement is false. The bottom nodes of the decision tree show the fraction of participants sorted into that node (The bottom number) and the fraction among those that are defined as "Sick" (The top number).

Figure 5.1 shows a decision tree based on the My Purchases cohort. Despite its simplicity, it shows some expected connections, although it is not perfect. As an example, participants who, on average, buy a low monthly average amount of "Cookies, crackers, biscuits and cakes", "Poultry", "Red meat" and a moderate/high amount of "Bread" and "Alcohol" (12% of the cohort) tend to be healthy 89%.

Figure 5.2

Figure 5.2 Variable importance for a random forest model. AverageTBE = Average time between purchases, ME = Maximum monthly amount, MeanOEPeriod = Average monthly purchase amount, TSE = Time since last purchase

In an attempt to capture interpretable spatial elements of the purchase data while reducing the total number of variables, we summarised each time series of purchases for every single defined food category into four variables: AverageTBE = Average time between purchases, ME = Maximum monthly amount, MeanOEPeriod = Average monthly purchase amount, and TSE = Time since last purchase.

We then seek to classify the overall self-reported health (Healthy or Sick) through a random forest model using the described variables. The importance estimate of each variable is shown in Figure 4. It is observed that the average purchases of Alcoholic drinks and Red meat, together with the time between Alcoholic drinks, seems to have the biggest impact on predicting an individual's self-reported health. It should be noted that the current accuracy of the random forest model is 57% in the test dataset, which is only slightly better than random guessing, though it is expected to increase substantially when more data becomes available in the SMIL cohort.

Plan for 2024: The main goal of 2024 is to run the pipeline and analytical approach on the larger SMIL cohort. This will enable us to look at the analysis of prevalent and incident diseases. We expect publication and dissemination in a medium to high-impact paper.

6. Collaboration and contributions from partners

A close collaboration with another Danish consumer cohort, using almost the same consumer data source, has been initiated. It will help WP4 meet its goals. Collaborating with another Danish cohort and recruiting participants from Storebox will enable joint research using data from +10000 participants. A PhD student from this project has visited SSI. The collaboration has already resulted in joint collaboration, and longitudinal analysis is underway. In addition, Researchers from Karolinska Institutet and Medical University of Graz, the Greater Capital Region of Zealand, and

The Danish Cancer Society have contributed to the joint publication "Assessing household lifestyle exposures from consumer purchases, The My Purchases cohort" as described previously. A technical description of the CPD enrichment pipeline is part of deliverables D6.2 and D4.3.

Together with researchers from the Greater Capital Region, an additional two publications are in the pipeline:

"Overweight in childhood and consumer purchases in a Danish cohort", PLOS ONE, a revised manuscript version, is currently under consideration.

"Cohort profile: The Health, Food, Purchases, and Lifestyle (SMIL) cohort - a Danish open cohort" has been successfully submitted online and is presently being considered for publication in BMJ Open. manuscript ID is bmjopen-2023-078773.

7. Scientific reporting

Scientific reporting and the results of the studies, not already published at the time of writing this deliverable report, will be described in the last periodic report of the HEAP project.

8. Summary

WP4 has successfully established and updated the recruitment of participants who consent to the continuous transfer of individual/household level CPD. A near real-time pipeline that enables identification of the products sold and enrichment of each product to enable broad assessment of individual exposures to nutrients, chemicals, and additives has been established as described in the published paper.

Further retrieval of individual-level information about health outcomes and trajectories was established through collaboration to enable longitudinal analysis of consumer data impact of household consumer exposures on health.

These results are preliminary, with expected scientific reporting in 2024.

Important information about citizens' attitudes towards consumer data collection will be used to design specifications of version 2.0 of the consumer data collection platform at mineindkob.ssi.dk used in HEAP.

9.

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